

**A STUDY ON PROBLEMS FACED BY WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN
KRISHNA DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH**

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ABSTRACT

It is now widely accepted that national development and women's development have to be purposeful and relevant. Women have to be full-fledged participants in economic activities. Participation of women, in economic activities is now emerging and a universal phenomenon. The problems encountered by women in unorganized sector are acute and innumerable and include meager wages, wage discrimination and casualisation. Women entrepreneurs are engaged in medium and large industrial units and other non-traditional establishments. They are not confined to commercial activities but venture into fields such as electronics, pharmaceuticals, engineering and services. The list of such successful entrepreneurs is quite long who have excelled not in India only but have thrived abroad. The constraints and problems of women entrepreneurs in India are immense and complex. The basic problem of a women entrepreneur stems from the fact that she is a female. Women are first seen as women and then as an entrepreneur. The Women entrepreneurs face various problem like teething troubles, license, inappropriate support, follow economics of scale, manufacturing and technical problems and human resource development.

KEYWORDS: Women Entrepreneurship, Problems And Prospects, Internal And External Factors.

1. WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA

With the pace of liberalization and privatization sweeping across the country and with the global business impact, the role of women as entrepreneurs and economic workers are already visible, the enterprising females are relatively a new breed of dynamic women in India.

It is now widely accepted that national development and women's development have to be purposeful and relevant. Women have to be full-fledged participants in economic activities. Participation of women, in economic activities is now emerging and an universal phenomenon.

All these trends indicate that the process of feminization of work force has caught currency in India, though it is not comparable in international perspective and is much lower than those in the developed western countries. Whether this trend of feminization of work force has led to women empowerment is doubtful as more than 80 percent of new jobs generated for rural women during 1981-91 were in the agricultural sector in which productivity as well as wages are very low leading to exploitation of labour. The present Government of A.P. has also given greater importance to the women Entrepreneur with the various Schemes. However, the problems encountered by women in unorganized sector are acute and innumerable and include meager wages, wage discrimination and casualisation.

Today we find women in different types of industries, conventional as well as non-conventional such as Engineering, Electronics, Handicrafts, Doll making, poultry, plastics, soap, ceramics, painting, toy making, nurseries, crèches, drugs, textile designing, dairy products, canning, Beauty Care center, knitting, Jewellery design etc.,

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In case of small scale manufacturing units, nearly 8 per cent are run exclusively by women entrepreneurs. Although the number of women entrepreneurs in one hand increase, yet proportionately it is small in comparison with the developed countries of the world. It is true that women participation in work force, self employment and entrepreneurial activity is disproportionately low due to certain constraints and taboos in the Indian Millen. The task of female entrepreneurship is full of challenges. They have to encounter public criticism, family prejudices and option and social constraints in the process of establishing themselves as independent entrepreneur.

1. Problems of Women Entrepreneurs in India

The constraints and problems of women entrepreneurs in India are immense and complex. The basic problem of a women entrepreneur stems from the fact that she is a female. Women are first seen as women and then as an entrepreneur. The basic ingredients such as independence and authority regained for successful entrepreneurs are not adequate for women in India. All this

results in the lower self-image, self-esteem and self-confidence of the woman. In most of the cases the male dominate the women. Risk bearing capacity which is a crucial factor in running and enterprise is very low among women. The low literacy rate among females is another serious hurdle move over, whatever the bookish knowledge she acquires in school, colleges and universities, is not sufficient to meet the problem of the business world.

The problem of liquidity and finance for women entrepreneurs still remains a major challenge. They lack access to external funds. Women face tougher security requirements as their lines of credit then do men. This is why the borrowings of women are only around 15 per cent of total borrowings from banks and financial institution. Women make up only a small proportion of the clients of most credit schemes. The women entrepreneurs more often, resort to borrowings form unscrupulous money lenders at lenders at exorbitant rates of interest.

Marketing is a major problem encountered in women entrepreneurs. It is slowly replacing finance as a major problem. The first major reason for the problems in marketing is that market competition has become much intensified due to the introduction of a wide variety of products posing a serious threat particularly to the survival of small entrepreneurs who depend on low level of technology.

Secondly, the competition from large scale units particularly the MNCs. In fact increasing Entrepreneurs who are unable to cut cost, which in itself is difficult in inflationary economy and fail to compete, will be forced to either innovation or restrict their operations in the areas of their strengths or stage an exit.

Third, because of fast mushrooming, of the small units, there is, at present, inter-unit competition within the small scale units themselves.

Fourth, consumers are becoming more and more sophisticated and product conscious. The Market for many products is fast changing from 'sellers to buyers' market.

Fifth at every level of marketing operation, there is the problem of middlemen who corner a considerable amount of margin that should accrue to women entrepreneurs. Due to lack of storing facilities, they are engaged in seasonal and agro based products and are forced to sell their products at lower price and middlemen taking advantage of the seasonal effects.

Sixth there is no lack of entrepreneurial skill even in villages and backward regions of the country but there certainly exists the problem of marketing the available skill. They feel less than equal in enhancing the value of their product by way of furnishing, packaging and advertising.

The Women entrepreneurs face various problem like teething troubles, license, inappropriate support, follow economics of scale, manufacturing and technical problems

and human resource development.

There are internal and external problems. As obvious, external problems are those which results from factors beyond the control of the entrepreneurs, the availability of power and other infrastructure facilities required for the smooth running of SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises). While internal problems affecting the industries relate to organization, structure, production channel, distribution channel, technical know-how, training, industrial relations and adequacy of management etc.,

2. Review of Literature:

An attempt is made to draw suggestions from the women entrepreneurs to improve women's participation in entrepreneurial development. Prior to this a review of some previous works is done to get better orientation towards proceeding with the study.

Lalitha Iyer in her study titled "Women Entrepreneurs, Challenges and strategies", deals with the efforts of women entrepreneurs in small scale industries in particular, the members of Association of Women Entrepreneurs of Karnataka (ANAKE) which is one of the pioneers in this field. She focuses on the hurdles women have to face as entrepreneurs and suggests strategies that could be adopted.

Paramjit Kaur Dhillon in her study titled, "Women Entrepreneurs, Problems and Prospects" analysed the motives of successful women entrepreneurs. She has analysed the various motives in starting up of an enterprise, the problems they faced, their attitude towards risks, their independent orientation, need for achievement and future planning and management. Dhillon also provides a list of institutions engaged in entrepreneur development programme and has an exhaustive list of government organization set up for the purpose.

Sheela Rani, in her study titled "A study of the problems of women Entrepreneurs in Chennai City" has assessed to evaluate the performance of women in entrepreneurial pursuit and analyzed the factors leading for the commencement of the business. An attempt was made in the study to find the competitiveness of women entrepreneurs and to study the problems affecting women entrepreneurs and their prospects in the future. It is found from the study that a major segment of the women entrepreneurs have faced managerial problems being absenteeism/turnover of employees, unable to control workmen and demand for increase in wages in Chennai City.

With this backdrop a study was taken up to interview 120 women entrepreneurs engaged in various business forms. The main focus of the study was to identify the problems faced by the women entrepreneurs of Krishna district.

3. Study on the Problems Faced by Women Entrepreneurs

There has been a High growth rate in small scale industries, especially for the last 15 years, among the women entrepreneurs in the Krishna district area. There is greater scope to increase the development of women entrepreneurs in Krishna district.

The various problems like Managerial, Marketing, Internal and External factors and domestic problems are analyzed in order to find the exact reason for the problems of women entrepreneurs. To study the prospects of the women entrepreneurs, the success over competitors and the rate of success has been analyzed.

About Krishna District:

Krishna district is named after the Krishna River which flows through the district. Machilipatnam is the administrative headquarters of the district. Vijayawada is the commercial center of the district and state. Krishna district is considered as the hub for pre-university education in Andhra Pradesh. Many medium Scale Cement factories are there throughout the district. There are many small scale industries like musical instruments at Jaggayyapeta, Rold gold ornaments at Machilipatnam and Kondapalli toys.

The women run industries are mainly caused due to "pull factors" rather than the "push factors". The Industries are traditional based and are mostly Priority units. They concentrate much on manufacture of food products like vermicelli, papad, pickles-making, textile and yarn manufacturing, art-silk yarn, twisting, gem cutting, beauty clinic etc.,

Special Problems Faced by Women Entrepreneurs

120 women entrepreneurs were examined to find whether they face any special problems and the response is tabulated in Table. 4. 1.

Table 4.1: Special Problems Faced by Women Entrepreneurs

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Faced	19	15.83
Notfaced	101	84.17
Total	120	100.00

Source: Primary Data

According to Table 4.1, out of 120 women entrepreneurs, it is found that around 84.17 percentage of them have not faced any special problems as entrepreneurs. However 15.83 percentage felt that they face problems being a women.

It is more evident from the table that most of the women entrepreneurs have not faced any special problems. Moreover very few women entrepreneurs face problems because of their gender.

Managerial Problems

Women entrepreneurs were opined to see whether they have any managerial problems. The above analysis was tabulated and presented in table 4.2

TABLE 4.2: Managerial Problems Faced by Women Entrepreneurs

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Faced	83	69.17
Not faced	37	30.83
Total	120	100

From Table 4.2 it is inferred that 69.17 percentage of women entrepreneurs faced managerial problems, and only 30.83% of them have not face by the Managerial problems.

It is observed that the majority of women entrepreneurs face managerial problems, because they do not have adequate managerial skills and knowledge. As more women entrepreneurs are well qualified in the relative fields, they require proper training to boost up hidden talents.

Types of Managerial Problems

The Various Types of Managerial problems have been analysed and presented in Table 4.3.

TABLE 4.3: Types of Managerial Problems Faced by Women Entrepreneurs

Type of Managerial problems	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Controlling Workmen	22	26.51
Motivating workers	14	16.87
Demands of Wage Increase	19	22.89
Heavy Absenteeism/ Turnover of Employees	28	33.73
Total	83	100

Source: Primary Data.

It is observed from table 4.3 that out of 83 women entrepreneurs who face managerial problems, 33.73 percentage, 26.51 percentage, 22.89 percentage and 16.57 percentage of them face the problems of heavy absenteeism or turnover of employees, could not control workmen, demands of wages increase and problems of motivating workers respectively.

It is evident from the data that a large portion of women entrepreneurs face problems like

heavy absenteeism and turnover of employees. Moreover the women entrepreneurs could not control their workmen.

Problems in Marketing

Women entrepreneurs were examined to find whether they have any difficulties in marketing their products and are presented in Table 4.4

TABLE 4.4: Difficulties Faced by Women Entrepreneurs in Marketing the Products

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Faced	25	20.83
Not Faced	95	79.17
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data.

It is inferred from table 4.4 that 20.83 percentage of the women entrepreneurs faced difficulties in marketing their products and 79.17 percentage have not faced any marketing problems. Majority of women entrepreneurs do not face any difficulties in marketing their products or service.

Types of Marketing Problems

The various problems faced by the women entrepreneurs in marketing are analyzing and presented in table 4.5

Table 4.5 : Type of Difficulties faced by women entrepreneurs in marketing their products

Types of Difficulties	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Heavy Competition	9	36.00
Lack of promotional Efforts	16	64.00
Total	25	100

Source: Primary Data.

From Table 4.5, it is found that out of the 25 women entrepreneurs who had faced difficulties, a large proportion of them (64 percentage) faced difficulties like lack of promotional efforts and (36 percentage) to heavy competition.

It is inferred from the data that majority of the women entrepreneurs face the difficulty of lack of promotional efforts in marketing their products.

Problems caused due to External Factors

Women Entrepreneurs were examined to find whether they have any problems due to external factors and is tabulated in table 4.6

TABLE 4.6 Whether Problems Caused to Women Entrepreneurs Due to External Factors

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Faced	89	74.17
Not Faced	31	25.83
Total	120	100

SOURCE: PRIMARY DATA.

It is observed from table 4.6 that 74.17 percentage of the women entrepreneurs faced problems due to external factors and 25.83 percentage have not faced any problems due to external factors. It is evident that majority of the women entrepreneurs face problems caused due to external factors.

Types of External problems

Table 4.7 shows the types of problems caused to women entrepreneurs due to external factors.

TABLE 4.7: Types of Problems Caused to Women Entrepreneurs Due to External Factors

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
Change in Government policies	12	13.48
Decrease in Demand	22	24.72
Shortage of Resources	15	16.85
Others	40	44.95
Total	89	100.00

Source: Primary Data.

It is found from table 4.7, that out of the 89 women entrepreneurs who had faced problems due to external factors, a large proportion of them 44.95 percentage faced problems due to various other causes, 24.72 percentage of them faced problems due to decrease in demand, 13.48 percentage shortage of resources and another 16.85 percentage difficulties due to change in government policies.

Thus, it is inferred that majority of the women entrepreneurs faced problems due to external factors because of various other causes.

Problems caused due to internal factors

Table 4.8 shows the problems caused to women entrepreneurs due to internal factors.

Table 4.8: Whether Problems Caused to Women Entrepreneurs Due to Internal Factors

PARTICULARS	No. of Respondents	Percentage
FACED	73	60.83
NOT FACED	47	39.17
TOTAL	120	100

Source: Primary Data.

It is evolved from table 4.8 that 60.83 percentage of women entrepreneurs faced internal problem while only 39.17 percentage have not faced any internal problem. It is clear from table 4.8, that majority of the women entrepreneurs faced internal problems.

Types of Internal problems

Table 4.9 highlights the type of problems caused to women entrepreneurs due to internal factors.

T a b l e 4 . 9 : Type of Problems Caused to Women Entrepreneurs Due to Internal Factors

Internal Causes	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Marketing problems	15	20.55
Lab our problems	33	45.20
Technical/ Operational problems	25	34.25
Total	73	100

Source: Primary Data.

According to Table 4.9, it is found that, out of the 73 women entrepreneurs who had faced problems due to internal causes, 45.20 percentage faced labour problems, 34.25 percentage faced technical and operational problems and 20.55 percentage faced labour problems.

It is inferred from the table that majority of the women entrepreneurs faced the problems due to internal causes like lab our problem and technical operational problems.

Major problems

The major problems faced by women entrepreneurs are analyzed and presented in Table 4.10.

Table 4.10: Major Problems Faced by Women Entrepreneurs

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Problems of Finance	32	26.67
Inadequate Government Support	16	13.33
Family Ties	33	27.50
Lack of Education	13	10.84
Male Dominance	7	5.83
Low Risk Bearing Ability	7	5.83
Limited Mobility of Funds	12	10.00
Total	120	100.00

Source: Primary Data.

It is observed from table 4.10, that 27.50 percentage, 26.67 percentage, 13.33 percentage, 10.84 percentage, 10 percentage, 5.83 percentage and 5.83 percentage of the women entrepreneurs faced major problems like family ties, finance, inadequate government support, lack of education, limited mobility of funds, male dominance and low risk bearing ability respectively. It is evident from the analysis that major proportion of women entrepreneurs faced major problems in the business due to family ties and finance.

Utilization of Incentive Schemes

Though women entrepreneurs were encouraged by the government as explained, it is of our interest to find out whether women entrepreneurs utilize such incentive schemes. Table 4.11 presents the utilization of incentive schemes given to women entrepreneurs.

Table 4.11: Utilization of Incentive Schemes Given To Women Entrepreneurs

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Utilized	47	39.17
Not- utilized	73	60.83
Total	120	100.00

Source: Primary Data.

According to table 4.11, 60.83 percentage of the women entrepreneurs have opined that they were not utilizing the incentive scheme offered by the government and only 39.17 percentage of women entrepreneurs are using incentive schemes offered by the Government. It is inferred from table that majority of women entrepreneurs do not use incentive schemes offered by the government.

Suggestions to improve women's participation

Women entrepreneurs were asked to give their suggestions to improve women's participation in entrepreneurs' development and the data are presented in Table 4.12.

Table 4.12: Suggestion to Improve Women's Participation in Entrepreneurs Development

Suggestions to improve women's participation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
By Government	11	9.17
Through women's Association	45	37.50
Financial Promotional Institutions	64	53.33
Total	120	100.00

Source: Primary Data.

From Table 4.12 it is inferred that around 53.33 percentages and 37.50 percentage of women entrepreneurs gave the opinion that prospective women entrepreneurs should be encouraged through financial/ promotional institutions and through women/s association. Only a very few percentage (9.17) opined that it can be encouraged by government. Thus, form the data. It is clear that women's participation in entrepreneurial development can be improved through financial promotional institutional and women's associations.

Success over Competition

The respondents have perceived the future prospects for women entrepreneurs, and are presented in Table 4.13.

TABLE 4.13: Success over Competition

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Successful	109	90.83
Not successful	11	9.17
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

From Table 4.13, it is found that most of the women entrepreneurs 90.83 percentage face responded that they have succeeded over their competitors, which only 9.17 percentage felt that have not succeeded. It is inferred from the table that most of the women entrepreneurs have succeeded over their competitors.

Rate of Success

The women entrepreneurs were analyzed to find how they had rated themselves and is tabulated in Table 4.14.

Table 4.14 : Rate of Success of Women Entrepreneur

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Highly successful	18	14.67
Moderately successful	19	16.00
Successful	83	69.33
Not successful	-	-
Total	120	100

Source: primary data.

It is observed from table 4.14 that 14.67 percentage of women entrepreneurs have rate themselves as moderately successful and the rest 69.33 percentage have rated themselves as

successful. It is clear from the table that most of the women entrepreneurs have rated themselves as successful.

Conclusion

Women entrepreneurs need guidance right from the formulation of the project till its execution. Along with financial aid, training plays a vital role in initiating and accelerating the process of Entrepreneurial development. The spirit of entrepreneurship can be nurtured to some extent by an appropriate pattern of education, awareness and training programmers. Adequate publicity should be given through television and radio at least one day in a week to create more awareness. Awareness has to be created among rural women for participation in nation building programmes. To encourage and educate them periodical seminars in collaboration with voluntary women organization should be conducted especially for women entrepreneurs. Loans to women entrepreneurs can be sanctioned at branch level itself to avoid the delay and a time schedule of one or two months can be proscribed for disposing of loan applications. The loan is to be disbursed in single installment. Officials from various agencies should work with a team spirit. Women entrepreneurs need a three year moratorium in turn loans provided by the financial institutions as against two years at present. Women's co-operation organization should be promoted to encourage women entrepreneurs. For women entrepreneurs Government should simplify the procedure for obtaining license from the state industries department. Indian women have traveled with the times for centuries and have proved to the world that the hand that rocks the cradle can rule the world. The promotion of women entrepreneurship alone would create a new dimension for their development. Thus, the women entrepreneurs can create and promote leadership qualities among women and also solve tomorrow's unemployment problem. The government, private financial institutions and women's associations should encourage and provide financial aid and support to women for them to become successful entrepreneurs.

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